

1 **Combination oral therapy for TNF resistance in IBD.**

2 Pre-Clinical/Clinical/Translational/Phase1-3
3 Compassionate Use Document (FDA format)

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8 1. The concept presented and being tested here: Jaki + 5-ASA for treatment resistance in TNFa inhibition.

- 9 a. Rationale: Broad spectrum immune targeting in the hematopoietic compartment with a Jaki
10 combined with gut epithelial inflammation control to reduce transmission of inflammation between
11 gut and hematopoietic compartments in order to maximize infliximab effectiveness through a
12 second systems-level approach.

13 2. Compassionate Use, also known as Expanded Access, provides access to an investigational
14 therapeutic (drug) when a life threatening condition exists and no comparable medication is available for
15 treatment.

- 16 3. The major requirements for Compassionate Use are:
17 a. The patient or patients has/have a life-threatening disease or medical condition.
18 b. There is no comparable or satisfactory alternative therapy
19 c. The potential benefit outweighs the potential risks
20 d. The use does not interfere with initiation, conduct or completion of clinical investigations.

21 4. Some significant fraction of patients who develop resistance to anti-TNF agents will experience an
22 unsafe and rapid deterioration in disease status, that features in some patients life-threatening restriction
23 to oral access resulting from obstruction or structure.

24 5. It is estimated that on average 99% of Expanded Access (Compassionate Use) are approved by
25 the FDA (Food and Drug Administration).

26 6. We used cells from healthy individuals and authentic tissues from affected patient cohorts,
27 measuring total transcription in response to blockade of TNF-alpha or in response to exposure to the
28 TNF-alpha cytokine to study mechanisms controlling resistance to clinical interventions (therapy) using
TNF-alpha inhibition in humans.

- a. Model systems were used only to conceptualize systems biologic concepts and provide information
regarding minimal components within an immunologic network.

7. The transcriptome-wide analysis also included discovery of individual gene targets likely to
function in conferring resistance to first-line biologic agents in gastroenterology.

8. For this approach, we measured total transcription using microarray in patient cells and tissues
resistant to infliximab or another biologic targeting TNF-alpha.

- a. In this proposal, we focus on resistance to TNFa inhibition by agents like infliximab, etanercept,
adalimumab or golimumab.
b. Resistance to biological targeting IL-23 like guselkumab is less well understood and addressed
separately.

1 9. We integrated findings from measurements of total transcription in separate cellular systems to
2 produce a concise and accurate biological description of cytokine interconnectedness and feedback
3 mechanisms in immunologic signaling.

4 10. We identified an inflammation propagating disease process involving cell to tissue communication
5 between the gut and the hematopoietic compartment in humans with established (diagnosed) disease.

- 6 a. Here, we propose the use of oral 5-ASA mesalamine agents (e.g., Pentasa), normally reserved for
7 patients with mild or moderate disease, to limit putative activation of systemic disease resulting
8 from inflammatory signaling derived from the gut, to which blood cells are exposed to.
- 9 b. This should occur concurrent with infliximab administration.

10 11. We pioneered the concept of a hematopoietic phenotype in humans with Crohn's Disease, one
11 that is highly responsive to disease activity, a phenotype we propose complicates understanding of
12 induction and maintenance of remission in humans with Crohn's Disease treatment with infliximab or
13 golimumab.

- 14 a. Here we propose that it follows that basic treatment of the hematopoietic compartment with a broad
15 spectrum inflammatory, like orally available JAK kinase inhibitors, will thus function to support or
16 enhance responsiveness to intravenous TNFa inhibition.

17 12. Thus, the formulation here proposes for the use of a selective JAK1 inhibitor (upadacitinib (Rinvoq))
18 combined with a eicasanoid-targeting 5-ASA mesalamine agent (Pentasa, Asacol) in patients being
19 treated with infliximab for severe Crohn's Disease.
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1 **Gut barrier breach is sufficient to induce inflammation in the hematopoietic compartment.**

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7 Gut barrier disruption with dextran sodium sulfate resulted in generation of hematopoietic cells with
8 activated inflammatory program gene expression with specific contribution from inflammatory component
9 genes of the arachidonate lipoxygenase (Alox), cyclooxygenase (Cox) and prostaglandin (PTG) families.

10 The experimental system enabled demonstration of sufficiency of gut barrier disruption for induction of
11 inflammation in cells of the blood.

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The data are pertinent for understanding of how inflammation might arise in an inflammatory bowel
disease, inflammation resulting from deficits in cells of the epithelial barrier but present in
hematopoietic-derived cells of the peripheral blood, including monocytes, providing insight into mechanism
of action in IBD pathogenesis including cell of origin and relative contributions of the epithelial cells of the
GI tract versus blood and immune cells from HSCs: disease activity in intestinal cells as compared to
disease activity in bone marrow-derived cells during instigation of inflammation and during active disease.

Mesalamine relieves gastrointestinal inflammation in *cis*.

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We examined the hypothesis that 5-aminosalicylates functioned topically in the lumen of the gastrointestinal tract and therefore possessed utility in enhancing clinical success of intravenous monoclonal antibodies that target TNF α in patients with severe disease: by enhancing effectiveness of the IV drug through reducing transmission or propagation of inflammation between the gut epithelial tissues and the hematopoietic compartment, and/or by minimizing the likelihood of developing resistance by modification of the hematopoietic milieu. In patient tissues from humans with the IBD ulcerative colitis, *ex vivo* mesalamine exposure in rectal explants resulted in relief of inflammation through antagonism of interleukin-1 β , of inflammatory cyclooxygenase and eicosanoid synthesis through targeting of the prostaglandin pathway (*PTGS2*) and by suppression of the sphingosine biosynthetic pathway. Mesalamine relieves inflammation in the gastrointestinal tract of humans with IBD and does so directly, in *cis*, through a topical mechanism involving reduction of inflammation through targeting of interleukin, prostaglandin and sphingosine pathways.

Citations

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1 **A hematopoietic phenotype in humans with Crohn's Disease.**

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7 The phenotype was heterogenous and included dysregulation of cellularity in erythroid (anemia), lymphoid
8 and myeloid (neutropenia) compartments. Hematopoietic defects observed in patients with IBD included
9 bone marrow failure phenotypes that possessed a stress component likely related to a DNA repair defect
10 and complicated at times by cellular stress resulting from extended nutritional deficiencies.

11 Citations

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Upadacitinib silences IL1b.

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We report here silencing of interleukin 1-beta by the chemical inhibitor of the Janus kinase JAK1 upadacitinib (Rinvoq). Thus, in a myeloid cell type that expressed the inflammatory cytokine IL-1b, a selective Jak1 inhibitor was able to silence it.

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